

PATOF: From the Past To the Future: Legacy Data in Small and Medium-Scale “PUNCH” Experiments - a Blueprint for PUNCH and Other Disciplines - D3 - Alpha version of the description of the FAIR Metadata Factory

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Abstract

This report describes the aims and objectives of the task package and the results delivered.

1 Introduction

1.1 Metadata Factory

Metadata generation is a crucial task for enhancing the FAIRness of scientific data from concrete experiments. With metadata preservation enabled for experiments in scientific institutes, the important and invaluable data derived from experiments can be preserved more easily and the FAIRness would become more achievable. Metadata Factory Pattern, is a framework that allows us to create related or dependent products that follows a general pattern. Metadata generated in general follows the schema from DataCite. Make changes and add additional stuff to the metadata according to the dataset from individual experiments. It will be discussed in the following section.

1.1.1 Design of the metadata schema in Metadata Factory - ALPS II

In order to generate XML metadata records that the schema of it is well-defined and well-organized, the metadata schema Fig.1 defined by DataCite is being used in the metadata generation process. As for the schema designed for the metadata generating consists of two layers, the top-layer metadata schema with common and generic metadata fields follows along the schema from DataCite. As the metadata schema defined by DataCite is well-established, also DataCite as a DOI register agency for research

Figure 1: The metadata schema that consist of two layers including the top layer (Core Metadata) and the second-layer (Experiment-specific Metadata).

data sets and it is used by a large number of research institutions in Germany. We decide to utilize the metadata schema from DataCite as the top-layer in this project. The concept of the top-layer metadata schema is that it emphasizes on basic but essential metadata information about a data set which focus on Findable and Accessible in FAIR principles.

As for the second-layer in the metadata schema, in which the metadata fields are designed based on the data provided by experts from concrete experiments. In this experiment-specific second-layer metadata schema it consist of more specific metadata about a data set derived from experiment. The idea of this layer in metadata schema is that it can be modified based on the requirements of each individual experiment and tailored to what it actually needs.

As for the metadata schema being designed, there are two types of metadata records that follow the schema being generated: One type of the records is mainly for DOI minting. It contains the bare minimum information that is needed when minting a DOI for a data set. In this type of metadata records the metadata fields in it basically follow what is defined in the top-layer metadata schema. On the other hand, the other type of metadata record contains a lot more information than just bare minimum. It contains not only the information defined in the top-layer metadata schema but the information in the second-layer metadata schema is also being used. Both types of metadata records are linked together.

1.1.2 Design of the core metadata schema in Metadata Factory

The following is the metadata fields in the preliminary metadata schema (top-layer) that is being designed based on the metadata requirements for the experiment ALPS II:

- identifier - the identifier of the dataset.
- creators - the person or persons that create the dataset.
- titles - the title of the dataset.

- subjects - the subject that refers to the topic of the dataset.
- contributors - the person or persons that make contribution to the dataset.
- publisher - the publisher of the dataset.
- publicationYear - the year of the publication of the dataset.
- resourceType - the resource type of the dataset, eg. book, article, dataset...

1.1.3 Design of the experiment-specific metadata schema (top-layer + second-layer) in Metadata Factory (taken the schema for ALPS II as an example)

- identifier - the identifier of the dataset.
- creators - the person or persons that create the dataset.
- titles - the title of the dataset.
- subjects - the subject that refers to the topic of the dataset.
- contributors - the person or persons that make contribution to the dataset.
- publisher - the publisher of the dataset
- publicationYear - the year of the publication of the dataset.
- resourceType - the resource type of the dataset, eg. book, article, dataset...
- DESY_ALPSIIinstrument - the metadata fields regarding the instrument used at DESY ALPS II experiment
 - device - the device or devices that is being used in the instrument
 - UUID - the universally unique identifier for the instrument
 - deviceType - the type of the device that is being used in the instrument
 - deviceName - the name of the device that is being used in the instrument
 - manufacturer - the manufacturer of the device for the instrument
 - firmwares - the firmware that is being used in the instrument
 - hardwares - the hardware that is being used in the instrument
 - dates - different dates relevant to the work of the instrument
 - network - the network setup for the instrument
 - formfactor - the size of the device
 - relatedItems - information about a resource related to the one being registered
 - installation - information about the installation of the instrument
 - specifics - extra or special information that is not categorized as the above-mentioned metadata fields

- DESY_ALPSII_software - the metadata fields regarding the software used at DESY ALPS II experiment
 - subsoftware - the finer category of the software that is being used in the experiment
 - contributors - the person or persons that make contribution to the software
 - contributorType - the type of contributor of the software
 - version - the version of the software
 - operationSystem - the operating system that is being used for the software
 - dates - different dates relevant to the work of the software
 - relatedItems - information about a resource related to the one being registered
 - installation - information about the installation of the instrument
 - specifics - extra or special information that is not categorized as the above-mentioned metadata fields

1.1.4 XML (Extensible Markup Language) for metadata record

For this use case we use XML (Extensible Markup Language) format files for the metadata records that will be created. The reasons of using XML file is that using XML format file as metadata storage is a widely used methods for a lot of German research institutes and DataCite, the largest DOI (Digital Object Identifier) registry also uses XML as the main metadata information storage for research data publication.

1.1.5 Software implementation for metadata records creation

In order to create metadata records using minimum human intervention, a software program will be developed for creating metadata records. As of the software implementation for creating metadata records (example of ALPSII dataset/metadata), we import the HDF5 files that will be provided by ALPSII experiment in the the workflow. In the HDF5 files it includes the data derived from the experiment and the metadata about the experiment, from the files information including metadata and the data attached to it, can be extracted.

Once the information in HDF5 files have been extracted, the data will be transformed into the format that is widely used and easily managed. In our case, XML format, with XML format the information extracted from HDF5 files will be mapped into the format that fits the metadata schema that has been designed and create XML metadata records Fig.2.

Figure 2: The example flowchart of the software implementation of generating metadata records.